

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action 2 - Cooperation Partnerships in School Education

REPORT

R4.2.2

Educational Programme Pilots

Co-funded by
the European Union

A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043

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WP Leader	Pepita
Main Author(s)	Giorgia Veneziano, Ivano Zoppi (Pepita)
Editor(s)	Giorgia Veneziano, Ivano Zoppi (Pepita)
Contributor(s)	Patrizia Giordano, Stefano Sanna (FPM); Stefania Cardinale, Cinzia Peschechera (Le Nius); Ana Filipa Oliveira, Teresa Sofia Castro (COFAC); Marko Divjak, Daša Grajfoner, Zvezdana Strmšek (DOBA); Lucie Brzáková (ProEduca); Lana Ciboci Perša, Tamara Kvas, Danijel Labaš, Igor Kanižaj (DKMK); Rosaria Favaro (ICS Bresso)
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Short Description	This document presents the results of the multi-country piloting of the ASAP Educational Programme carried out between 2023 and 2025 in formal and non-formal educational settings. It documents the implementation of successive pilot phases across partner countries (Italy, Croatia, Czechia, Portugal and Slovenia), involving pre-adolescents, teachers, parents and school leaders. The report analyses the feasibility, clarity, engagement and educational impact of the Learning Units, and consolidates evidence to support the refinement, scalability and transferability of the ASAP Educational Programme.

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Introduction

The present report summarises the implementation and validation process of the ASAP Educational Programme, carried out through a structured piloting pathway over multiple phases. The work aimed to test the programme in real educational environments, assessing feasibility, clarity, learning impact and long-term sustainability.

Across the piloting stages, the Learning Units were delivered in school and non-formal educational settings, involving students, teachers, educators and families. The programme structure allowed gradual expansion: from early prototyping to wider implementation and autonomous delivery by trained facilitators. The methodology adopted — experiential, reflective and cooperative — has proven applicable to different educational contexts, supporting emotional awareness, critical questioning and responsible digital behaviour.

This document compiles the overall results of the piloting work, providing a comprehensive overview of the processes, feedback and insights that have contributed to the refinement of the educational tools and to the final definition of the ASAP model.

1. Italy

1.1. Pilot 0

Introduction and context

Pilot 0 represented the first concrete experimentation phase of the ASAP Educational Programme, with the primary aim of validating, in real-life conditions, the theoretical model developed within WP3 and collecting useful feedback to refine the Learning Units (LUs) and methodological strategies. This phase took place between **February 2023 and January 2024**, within both school and oratory settings located across **Lombardy, Piedmont and Umbria**: ICS Bresso, Milan, Monza, Bardonecchia and Perugia.

The territorial context is characterised by complex educational environments, consisting of lower secondary schools and extracurricular youth-aggregation spaces (oratories and youth centres) in which Pepita operates on a permanent basis as a social cooperative. The selection of these locations made it possible to test the LUs in different scenarios, ensuring a broader and more diversified assessment of the methodology.

The coordination of the pilot was managed by Pepita (responsible for the educational implementation and facilitation of the workshops), in collaboration with FPM (methodological and monitoring leadership), Le Nius (communication and media-content support) and ICS Bresso (school partner for the first experimentation of the “Cooperative Editorial Board”).

The main objective was to verify the effectiveness of the ASAP educational model, based on a metacognitive, experiential and participatory approach designed to foster awareness, critical reflection and digital empathy among adolescents.

Target and participants

Pilot 0 involved a total of **298 students** (age group 11–13 years), **32 parents**, **5 teachers** and **1 school principal**, as well as **researchers and educators** from the Italian partners.

The distribution by location was as follows:

- **Milan:** 137 students
- **Monza:** 70 students
- **Bardonecchia:** 58 students
- **Bresso:** 33 students, 5 teachers, 1 school leader
- **Perugia:** 32 parents

The activities were carried out mainly within local schools and oratories. No additional external figures were involved, apart from the educators and trainers internal to the partner organisations.

Learning Units piloted

The Learning Units implemented in this phase were selected based on their educational relevance and were only lightly adapted to the characteristics of the groups and contexts, while preserving the methodological structure of the ASAP Programme and ensuring its replicability.

During Pilot 0, three Learning Units were mainly tested:

- **Emotions**
- **The Power of Questions**
- **Authenticity & Sources**

These LUs, intended for the **pre-adolescent** target, were conducted with **laboratory and metacognitive** methods, using cooperative games, guided reflection exercises, role-playing, group activities and circular discussions. The sessions had an **average duration of 45–60 minutes**, with a maximum of two hours in the laboratories of the "Cooperative Editorial Board" at ICS Bresso.

The work focused on the **ability to recognize and manage emotions**, critical **reflection on language and online sources**, and the use of **question as a thought tool**. The LUs used in this phase turned out to be **very close to the final version then integrated into the ASAP Handbook**, with minimal adaptations regarding the sequence of activities and the language.

Implementation and methodology

Pilot 0 has adopted a simple and flexible format, with a **meeting for each group**, lasting about **45-60 minutes** (extendable up to two hours for school groups). In the case of the **Cooperative Editorial Board (CEB)** of Bresso, the activities have been included within the afternoon workshops of the secondary school, in continuity with the path of active citizenship already in place.

Coordination between the Italian partners was constant: each partner conducted the experimentation of the LUs of their own design, collectively participating in the meetings at ICS Bresso to share observations and strategies. Among the main **organizational challenges**, time management and the need to adapt language to different age groups emerged; these critical issues were addressed through joint briefings and moments of post-activity reflection.

The methodological approach was based on **metacognition, direct experience and active involvement of the participants**: the students were invited to reflect not only on the contents, but on the way they thought, felt and interacted.

Evaluation and feedback

The evaluation of Pilot 0 was based on **satisfaction questionnaires and qualitative observations** collected at the end of the workshops. According to the data reported in the monitoring documents, the **percentage of positive responses was 100%** in the context of the CEB in Bresso, with a high level of satisfaction with both the content and the methodology.

Some significant qualitative evidence emerges from the shared comment document:

- the students appreciated the use of interactive tools (games, Kahoot, LEGO, visual brainstorming);
- teachers reported an increase in participation and reflective capacity in the children;
- the emotional component was "highly engaging" and "useful for creating climate and trust";
- the need to expand the moments of group discussion and to provide a more relaxed time for collective restitution was noted.

Key Findings and Key Insights

Pilot 0 made it possible to validate the basic structure of the ASAP educational program and to identify some **operational indications for its evolution**.

Key findings include:

- **Confirmation of the validity of the metacognitive method** in promoting critical thinking and reflection on emotions.
- **Effectiveness of the workshop format** and the playful-participatory dimension in involving pre-adolescents.
- **Importance of the role of the educator as a facilitator**, rather than as a transmitter of content.
- **There is a need for more space for shared reflection** and linguistic adaptations that are more calibrated by age and context.
- **Need to strengthen the involvement of parents**, whose participation remains partial.

The tested Learning Units were subsequently updated with minor **changes in the formulation of the guiding questions and in the introduction of the reflection phases**, based on feedback from the CEB and other experiments.

Conclusion and next steps

Pilot 0 provided a solid basis for the subsequent phase of international experimentation, offering concrete evidence on the **functionality, attractiveness and replicability** of the ASAP educational program. The results of this first experience have guided the planning of **Pilot 1**, in particular for:

- the choice of priority Learning Units (“Emotions” e “Power of Questions”);
- the adoption of a more structured **impact evaluation format** (T0–T1–T2);
- the extension of piloting to other school and oratory contexts.

The joint work of the Italian partners demonstrated the coherence between the theoretical model developed in WP3 and its application in real educational settings, and supported the development of a genuinely *transversal* approach connecting schools, local communities and third-sector organisations.

1.2. Pilot 1

Introduction and context

Pilot 1 represented the first official phase of experimentation of the ASAP Educational Programme following Pilot 0, with the objective of testing the clarity, transferability and effectiveness of the already prototyped Learning Units (LUs) in different contexts, and of collecting comparable feedback from diverse target groups (pre-adolescents, parents, teachers).

The implementation period ran from November 2023 to May 2024, in Lombardy and Umbria, with activities carried out in lower and upper secondary schools as well as in oratories. The main settings included: ICS Bresso, “Jacopone da Todi” High School (Todi), Astrolabio Oratory (Perugia), Oratory (Spoleto), “Bottoni” Scientific High School (Milan), Vivaio School (Milan) and “Santa Caterina da Siena” School (Milan).

In continuity with Pilot 0, Pilot 1 confirmed the ASAP approach oriented towards reflective thinking and active participation, with an increased learning-by-doing component compared to metacognition

alone, in order to foster engagement and practical applicability both in classrooms and in community educational settings.

Target and participants

Overall, in Italy Pilot 1 involved:

- **295 students** (pre-adolescents, **11–13 years old**);
- **49 parents**;
- **1 school leader**.

Distribution by location (as per internal reconnaissance):

- **Bresso**: 11 students + 1 head teacher (CEB/continuity with Pilot 0)
- **Todi (Liceo Jacopone da Todi)**: 68 students
- **Perugia (Oratorio Astrolabio)**: 110 students
- **Spoletto (Oratory)**: 29 parents
- **Milan – "Bottoni" Scientific High School**: 46 students
- **Milan – Nursery School**: 20 parents
- **Milan – "Santa Caterina da Siena" School**: 60 students

The **teachers** participated mainly as **observers** and context facilitators.

Learning Units piloted

The Learning Units implemented in this phase were selected based on their educational relevance and were only lightly adapted to the characteristics of the groups and contexts, while maintaining the methodological structure of the ASAP Programme and ensuring its replicability.

The LUs developed by the Italian partners **in the previous cycle** were tested:

- **The Power of Questions**
- **Emotions**
- **Authenticity & Sources**

Format and duration: The meetings in the school environment normally covered **two consecutive school hours (45' + 45')**, with **about 45 minutes per** single hourly unit; **in each meeting, two activities** taken from the selected LU were usually proposed, **but in some contexts a greater number of activities were tested** when time permitted.

Methods and tools. Interactive workshops with **cooperative games, guided activities, short metacognitive discussions, rapid reworking**, use of **paper materials and visual aids**; light adaptations to language and examples according to the group and the setting (class/oratory).

Implementation and methodology

The **operational format** included cycles of **1-2 meetings per group** (school/oratory), each lasting **about 90 minutes** (two school modules), conducted by **educators and teachers as observers**. In high schools, attention was paid to the **relevance of examples** and the **acceleration of activation times**.

Coordination. Methodological alignment and exchange of observations between the Italian partners, with the use of **observation schemes and debrief notes** to track changes and learnings between one context and another.

Criticalities and management

- **Tight deadlines** in some complexes → targeted selection of activities, reduction of redundant parts, **clear deliveries**.
- **Group heterogeneity** (age, class climate) → **structured facilitation** and linguistic micro-adaptations.
- The involvement of parents was uneven, as it was highly dependent on the availability of schools/youth centres and the possibility of organising meetings outside school hours (afternoon/evening). In the realities more accustomed to proposals for parents, it was easier to get involved.

Evaluation and feedback

Instruments. The evaluation was based on **qualitative observations** and **short local factsheets/feedback**; the common definition of the framework continued at partnership level.

Qualitative evidence (summary):

- **Students:** good level of **satisfaction** with practical activities; **quick entry games** (e.g. ice-breaker) and moments of **short guided discussion** appreciated; "**a little more time**" required to deepen.
- **Teachers:** perceived **didactic usefulness** and **readiness to use** the worksheets; suggested a **greater explicitness of the instructions** for some activities and **more structured** discussion prompts.
- **Parents:** good **perceived relevance** of the contents (emotions, authenticity of the sources) and interest in **continuing with longer meetings**; practical examples **on communication in the family** are requested.

Synthetic data. In the absence of consolidated quantitative indicators for all locations, there is a **generally positive qualitative assessment** and a **good feasibility** of the format in the school time.

Key Findings and Key Insights

- **Effective learning-by-doing:** the alternation of **short activation** → **guided reflection** → **re-elaboration** supports involvement and understanding, even in large groups.
- **Replicability:** LUs are **transferable** to heterogeneous contexts (school/oratory) with **minimal adaptations** (language, examples, times).
- **Facilitation as a lever:** the **quality of the conduction** (clear instructions, time management, follow-up questions) has a significant impact on climate and participation.
- **Parents: interest but low continuity:** we need a **longer and more modular offer**, with concrete examples of **communication and emotions in the family**.
- **Materials:** useful and "**ready to use**", but with the need for **more explicit instructions** and **more guided prompts for teachers**.

Micro-adaptations introduced after Pilot 1

- clarification of some **deliveries** and **times for activities**;
- adding **contextual examples**;

Conclusion and next steps

Pilot 1 acted as a **bridge** between prototype validation and **large-scale dissemination**: the evidence collected confirms the **feasibility** of the program in school time (45' + 45' modules) and in local educational spaces, with **good engagement** of children and **interest** of teachers and families.

For **Pilot 2 and 3** it is recommended to:

- prepare the test of the **impact framework (T0–T1–T2)** in some locations;
- provide teachers **with quick guides** with more detailed instructions and prompts;

In summary, Pilot 1 in Italy **confirms the solidity of the** ASAP Educational Program and provides clear operational indications for the improvement of **facilitation instructions** and for the **harmonization of impact assessment in the** subsequent phases.

1.3. Pilot 2

Introduction and context

Pilot 2 represented the **expansion and consolidation** phase of the ASAP educational program in Italy, following the methodological validation of Pilot 1. The goal was to test the **scalability** of the *Learning Units* (LUs) in larger educational contexts and with trained conductors, as well as to verify the clarity and replicability of the training material.

The construction period is between **October and December 2024**, in collaboration with schools and oratories in Lombardy and Umbria:

- **ICS Bresso** (fourth edition of the *Collaborative Editorial Board*),
- **Oratorio Astrolabio (Perugia)**,
- **Zaccaria Institute (Milan)**,
- **San Carlo Institute (Milan)**.

The activities took place during school hours and in the afternoon workshops, with the educational coordination of **Pepita**, the methodological support of **FPM** and the documentation/dissemination of **Le Nius**.

Target and participants

The pilot involved overall:

- **328 students (11–13 years old)**,
- **62 teachers**,
- **85 parents**,
- **1 school leader**.

Distribution by location:

- **Bresso**: 186 students, 13 teachers, 1 school leader;
- **Milan**: 107 students, 29 teachers, 40 parents (Zaccaria and San Carlo);

- **Perugia:** 35 students, 20 teachers, 45 parents (Astrolabio).

Learning Units piloted

The Learning Units adopted in this phase have been selected on the basis of their educational relevance and lightly adapted to the characteristics of the groups and contexts, maintaining the methodological structure of the ASAP program and ensuring its replicability.

During Pilot 2, three LUs were implemented and adapted:

- **The Power of Questions**
- **Emotions**
- **Authenticity & Sources**
- **Communication**

Format and Duration

Each group participated in **two consecutive meetings of 45–60 minutes** (or a single workshop of about 90 minutes in the speakers). In each session, **one or two activities per module were proposed**, selected from those provided for in the manual.

Methodologies included **cooperative games, reflection exercises, guided discussions, and short graphic or narrative reworkings**. The materials used were paper and visual, with linguistic and rhythmic micro-adaptations based on age and context.

Implementation and methodology

Pilot 2 maintained the **experiential and participatory approach**, experimenting with the **replicability of LUs** by trained conductors not directly involved in their design.

Coordination between Italian partners was ensured through **periodic monitoring meetings**, post-activity discussions and sharing of observations collected in the various locations.

Main critical issues encountered:

- tight deadlines due to school schedules;
- different levels of involvement by teachers;
- the need to adapt language and tools in extracurricular contexts.

Strategies adopted:

- more targeted selection of activities and simplification of deliveries;
- introduction of short briefings with teachers for methodological alignment;
- attention to the final phase and the group debrief as a moment of shared synthesis.

Evaluation and feedback

At this stage, **the final version of the project's Impact Evaluation Framework has not yet been applied**, as common tools were being defined. The evaluation was based on **direct qualitative observations** and **short feedback collected verbally or through local cards** at the end of the workshops.

Main qualitative evidence:

- **Students:** high involvement, appreciation for the practical approach and freedom of expression; request for longer times for some activities.
- **Teachers:** they judge the LUs as "clear and immediately usable", while suggesting more detail in the prompts and operating instructions.
- **Parents:** they evaluate the content positively (in particular on emotions and authenticity online), showing interest in more frequent or cyclical meetings.

These observations contributed to the **revision of the materials** and the **shared definition of future evaluation guidelines** within the partnership.

Key Findings and Key Insights

- **Scalability confirmed:** the model proves to be effective and reproducible even by trainers who are not authors of the LUs.
- **Facilitation as a key lever:** the quality of the conduct and the clarity of the deliveries directly influence the involvement of the participants.
- **Ready-to-use materials:** appreciated for their structure and adaptability, but to be made more detailed in the indications.
- **Family involvement:** positive but still discontinuous; parents ask for moments of practical discussion.
- **Strengthening of the educational network:** growing collaboration between school, oratory and local educational institutions.

Conclusion and next steps

Pilot 2 consolidated the methodological and operational validity of the ASAP program in Italy, demonstrating that Learning *Units* can be **replicated autonomously** and maintain methodological consistency and educational outcomes.

The evidence collected contributed to:

- define **clearer criteria for the conduct and adaptation of LUs**;
- structuring a **shared qualitative assessment** at European level;
- orient **Pilot 3** towards the comparative collection of good practices and the final development of the **Open & Flexible Handbook**.

In summary, Pilot 2 marked the transition from methodological testing to the **consolidation and pre-dissemination phase**, strengthening the link between school education, territory and digital citizenship skills.

1.4. Pilot 3

Introduction and general context

Pilot 3 represented the final phase of the experimentation process of the *ASAP Educational Programme* in Italy, aimed at the **definitive validation of the educational model** and the verification of its **autonomous replicability** in school and oratory contexts.

After the consolidation phase of Pilot 2, Pilot 3 aimed to test the ability of **educators and teachers trained** in the *Training Programme (WP5)* to independently conduct the *Learning Units* and to adapt them to the needs of their group-class or educational context.

The activities took place between **January and June 2025** in Lombardy and Umbria, in continuity with the territorial networks already activated in previous pilots.

The partners involved were **Pepita, FPM** and **Le Nius**, in collaboration with local schools and oratories. Pilot 3 was divided into two complementary phases:

- **Phase 3A**, dedicated to the coordination and accompaniment of the transition towards the autonomy of trainers;
- **Phase 3B**, in which the activities were carried out directly by **educators and teachers trained** in the Training Programme.

Phase 3A – Coordinated Implementation & Transition

Phase 3A aimed to consolidate the ASAP methodology and prepare trainers for the autonomous implementation expected in the following phase. The activities were conducted by Pepita and Le Nius, with methodological supervision by FPM, in some contexts previously piloted in earlier phases (schools and oratories in Bresso, Milan and Perugia), as well as in new contexts involved specifically in this stage.

The Learning Units implemented in this phase were selected based on their educational relevance and were lightly adapted to the characteristics of the groups and contexts, while maintaining the methodological structure of the ASAP Programme and ensuring its replicability.

The Learning Units *have been proposed*:

- **Emotions,**
- **The Power of Questions,**
- **Authenticity & Sources,**
- **Communication,**

adapted to the needs of different groups (students 11–13 years old, teachers and parents). Each meeting lasted between **45 and 90 minutes**, with an approach centered on experience, guided reflection and the co-construction of meanings.

The **feedback** collected indicates a high level of involvement from students and a growing sense of mastery from teachers who had already participated in previous phases of the project. Parents expressed particular interest in activities related to emotions and effective communication.

Phase **3A** made it possible to:

- further test the **clarity of instructions** and the **usability of** the program materials;
- collect useful observations to simplify and harmonize the *Learning Units*;
- select the group of trainers who would conduct phase **3B**.

Phase 3B – Implementation by Trained Educators

Phase **3B** represented the **final experimentation of autonomy**: the activities of the ASAP program were carried out **directly by educators and teachers trained** through the *Training Program* developed by Pepita and Le Nius.

Training of trainers

The training course involved a total of **74 trainers**, divided between:

- **Istituto Puecher Rinnovata Pizzigoni** (Milan): 12 teachers,
- **Pepita Educators: 37** (in two separate sessions),
- **Le Nius Staff**: 3 members,
- **Pepita Staff**: 22 members.

The training took place **online and in person**, with modules dedicated to the ASAP methodology, the conduct of the workshops and the collection of qualitative feedback.

Field implementation

The activities were carried out independently within local contexts (schools and oratories), with light monitoring by Pepita and Le Nius, who provided methodological support and periodic opportunities for discussion. The Learning Units most frequently used were *Emotions*, *The Power of Questions* and *Communication & Empathy*, often combined into short programmes of two or three sessions. The trained educators highlighted the clarity and adaptability of the materials and the possibility of integrating the activities easily into their daily educational practice. Some also emphasised the need for further practical examples and quick evaluation tools.

Feedback and observations

- **Students**: high degree of participation and interest; activities perceived as stimulating and "different from the usual".
- **Teachers/Educators**: satisfaction with the operational approach and the flexibility of the method; the step-by-step structure of the manual was appreciated.
- **Parents**: positive feedback especially on activities related to communication and emotional management.

Phase 3B therefore confirmed the **autonomous replicability of the ASAP program**, showing how the methodology can be used effectively by trainers not belonging to the original development team.

Evaluation and feedback

Impact assessment (T0–T1): In Pilot 3, a first test of the impact assessment framework (T0–T1) was introduced, applied exclusively to phase 3A and only to the "Emotions" Learning Unit.

The test was carried out only in oratory contexts, where it was possible to work with stable groups, keeping the same educator and the same participants between T0 and T1. The locations involved were:

- Oratorio Lentate (56 students)
- Verano Brianza (30)
- Cesano Maderno (63)
- Oratories of Seregno (125)

In total, 274 students participated in the pre/post assessment, equal to 58% of the students involved in Phase 3A (469 students).

The evaluation was based on two essential tools:

- Pre/post questionnaire with real situations (T0–T1), administered to students before and after the activity;
- Observational grid compiled by the educator, focused on participation, use of emotional language, relational dynamics and emotional recognition.

The preliminary results (to be verified) show:

- improvement in the recognition and labelling of emotions;
- greater awareness of one's emotional experience during the activity;
- increase in willingness to listen and expressive language;
- group climate perceived as more cooperative.

None of the activities of Phase 3B involved the application of the T0-T1 protocol, since the experimentation was concentrated in the contexts of 3A considered most suitable for pre/post monitoring.

Key Findings and Key Insights

- **Autonomy of the trainers:** the trained educators conducted the LUs in a coherent way, demonstrating mastery and adaptability.
- **Clarity and flexibility of materials:** the manual and the sheets were easy to use, with only minimal simplifications required.
- **Involvement and participation:** students and teachers showed a high level of engagement and a better relational climate.
- **Development of the territorial network:** expansion of the number of schools and oratories interested in joining the model.
- **Contribution to the final version of the Handbook:** Feedback from trainers has guided the latest revisions of the *ASAP Open & Flexible Handbook*.

Conclusion

Pilot 3 in Italy marked the conclusion of the testing phase and the final validation of the ASAP model. The combination of Phase 3A (coordination and support) and Phase 3B (autonomous implementation by trained facilitators) made it possible to verify the sustainability, scalability and educational effectiveness of the programme.

The evidence collected confirms that the Learning Units are reproducible, adaptable and culturally flexible, and that the network of trained educators now represents a stable asset for the dissemination of the model within the national context.

Pilot 3 therefore contributed to the final drafting of the *ASAP Open & Flexible Handbook* and laid the foundations for future dissemination and training actions at both territorial and European level.

2. Croatia

Pilots in Croatia were implemented in 12 primary schools, mainly located in Zagreb and its surrounding areas. During the first and second pilot phases, only the associated partner schools participated in the implementation. In the third phase, the project partner DKMK expanded the reach of the programme by involving additional schools that had expressed a specific need for support in the field of digital literacy, emotional education, and online communication.

In the first pilot phase, the selected and tested learning activities were taken from the *Emotions* learning unit, focusing on helping preadolescents recognise, express, and manage emotions both online and offline. The second pilot phase was dedicated to testing activities from the *Role Models* learning unit, encouraging critical reflection on influences, values, and behavioural patterns encountered on social media and in daily interactions. In the third pilot phase, schools were granted the freedom to choose the learning activities most relevant to their specific needs and priorities. The majority of participating schools selected activities from the *Communication* learning unit, confirming the strong interest of teachers and parents in strengthening constructive and empathetic communication skills among preadolescents.

Pilot 1 engaged a total of 160 participants, Pilot 2 reached 310 participants, Pilot 3 involved 752 participants. Altogether, over 1,222 individuals, including preadolescents, parents, and teachers took part in the Croatian implementation of the ASAP Educational Programme. These pilots not only tested the clarity and feasibility of the educational materials but also demonstrated a high level of motivation and engagement among both educators and learners, reinforcing the importance of such programmes in contemporary school environments.

2.1. Pilot 1

General introduction to the pilot

Pilot 1 was implemented in March and April 2024 at Primary School Kustošija and Primary School Većeslava Holjevca in Zagreb. The pilot engaged a total of 160 participants, including 60 preadolescents, 38 parents and 60 teachers.

The activities selected and tested in this phase were drawn from the Learning Unit *Emotions*, focusing on developing emotional awareness, empathy, and self-regulation in both online and offline contexts. The sessions aimed to encourage reflection on emotional experiences, recognition of different emotional expressions, and understanding how emotions influence behaviour and communication.

The implementation of Pilot 1 provided valuable insights into how preadolescents, parents and teachers perceive and manage emotions in the digital age. Through interactive exercises, guided discussions, and collaborative activities, participants were encouraged to explore the role of emotions in online interactions and everyday relationships.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

Pilot 1 was implemented in May and June 2024 at Primary School Kustošija and Primary School Većeslava Holjevca in Zagreb. The pilot engaged 60 preadolescents.

The activities selected and tested during this phase were based on the Learning Unit *Emotions*, which aims to foster emotional awareness, empathy, and self-regulation among preadolescents. Work with preadolescents was organised in three separate groups of approximately 20 students each, ensuring active participation and a safe, supportive environment for sharing personal experiences and opinions. Each group participated in two 45-minute sessions, implemented in classroom settings. The sessions focused on recognising emotions, expressing feelings appropriately, and understanding how emotions influence online and offline behaviour. Interactive activities Emoji stories and Bingo were used to encourage open dialogue and active engagement.

Feedback was collected through short paper-based surveys completed at the end of each session. The majority of students described the activities as fun, engaging, and relatable. They particularly enjoyed working with emojis and participating in group discussions about how emotions are expressed on social media. Many highlighted that the sessions helped them realise how easily online communication can lead to misunderstandings and how important it is to pause and reflect before reacting emotionally. Pilot 1 demonstrated that the Emotions learning unit is highly effective and adaptable for Croatian school settings. It was particularly successful in helping preadolescents recognise and articulate emotions, understand the emotional context of online interactions and build empathy toward peers.

Pilot with parents

A dedicated 60-minute session was organised for parents to present the activities carried out with preadolescents and to discuss the main conclusions drawn from the Emotions learning unit. The discussion focused on what children had learned about online emotional awareness, safe communication, and self-control in digital interactions. Parents explored how emotions influence online behaviour and were encouraged to reflect on their own communication patterns and the messages they convey to their children.

Parents appreciated the opportunity to see what their children had been learning and to discuss how these lessons could be continued at home. They agreed that these principles are crucial for fostering responsible digital habits, emotional intelligence, and open communication between parents and children. The session helped parents better understand how to talk with their children about emotions, privacy, and behaviour in digital spaces, reinforcing the importance of calm, thoughtful, and empathetic online interactions.

In the evaluation, parents expressed that they enjoyed the lecture and emphasised that there should be more activities of this kind organised for parents. They highlighted that such sessions help them better understand their children's online experiences, improve family communication, and provide simple, effective tools for guiding children toward more responsible and emotionally aware online behaviour.

Pilot with teachers

A 60-minute workshop was conducted with 60 teachers to introduce and discuss the Emotions learning activities. Teachers reviewed the materials, reflected on their classroom applicability, and shared insights based on their experience with emotional education. Feedback was collected verbally and through written forms. Teachers described the activities as creative, modern, and suitable for raising awareness about emotional literacy in the digital age. They particularly appreciated that the

activities could be easily integrated into their regular teaching practice without requiring extensive preparation, making them practical and accessible for everyday classroom use.

During the reflection, teachers emphasised that emotional awareness is a critical skill for preadolescents, especially given the emotional impact of social media and online interactions. Many recognised that students often struggle to manage emotions triggered by online comparisons, likes, and comments. As one teacher noted, “Social media affects their mood more than they realise, likes, comments and comparisons hit them hard.” Another teacher explained, “So many conflicts in class start with students not knowing how to handle their emotions.”

Teachers agreed that the Emotions learning unit provides valuable tools to help students identify, express, and regulate their feelings constructively. They also highlighted that such lessons help prevent behavioural issues and create a more positive, supportive classroom atmosphere. Teachers expressed strong enthusiasm for the Emotions learning unit, appreciating its clarity, flexibility, and immediate relevance. They suggested continuing to develop similar activities that combine emotional literacy with media awareness, as these topics address real and urgent needs in the daily lives of students.

Conclusion

Pilot 1 clearly confirmed the relevance, effectiveness, and adaptability of the Emotions learning unit within the Croatian school context. Implemented across three groups of preadolescents, as well as with parents and teachers, the pilot demonstrated strong engagement, practical value, and emotional depth across all target groups. Overall, Pilot 1 demonstrated that the Emotions learning unit effectively supports preadolescents’ emotional intelligence and digital well-being, while also engaging parents and teachers as active partners in the process. The main recommendations for future implementation include providing slightly more time for reflection, strengthening facilitation guidance, and continuing to integrate emotional literacy education as a regular part of school and family life.

2.2. Pilot 2

General introduction to the pilot

Pilot 2 was implemented in November and December 2024 in three primary schools in Zagreb; Primary School Većeslava Holjevca, Primary School Kustošija, and Primary School Jelkovec. The pilot engaged a total of 310 participants, including 128 preadolescents, 78 teachers and 101 parents.

The activities selected and tested during this phase were taken from the Learning Unit *Role Models*, designed to help students critically analyse the influence of digital media, influencers, and social networks, and to promote reflection on values, authenticity, and healthy self-image. Through interactive exercises and guided discussions, participants explored the question Who influences me and why and learned to recognise the difference between external appearance and genuine personal qualities.

The implementation of Pilot 2 offered important insights into how preadolescents interpret and imitate online behaviour and how teachers and parents can guide them toward greater self-awareness, independence and emotional stability.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

The Role Models learning unit was implemented with six groups of students in Primary School Većeslava Holjevca and Primary School Kustošija, involving a total of 128 preadolescents aged 11–13. Each group participated in one or two 45-minute sessions, carried out in November 2024. The sessions were based on the presentation and interactive workshop *Role Models and Values*, designed to help students reflect on the people and influences that shape their beliefs, behaviour and aspirations. Through guided discussion, students explored what values are, how they are formed, and how they influence the way we act and relate to others.

The workshop began with a discussion on what values mean, followed by an activity where students identified which values they consider most important, such as friendship, honesty, respect, and fairness and where these values come from (family, peers, teachers, sports coaches or public figures). Students were encouraged to distinguish between real-life influences (family members, friends, teachers) and media influences (celebrities, athletes, influencers). Together, they analysed how social networks, video games, and online trends can shape opinions, emotions, and behaviour.

Feedback collected through paper questionnaires and group reflection showed that students greatly enjoyed the workshop and were highly engaged in discussions about values and influence. Many shared that they had never thought about the topic in this way before and that the activity helped them realize the importance of being aware of who influences them and of developing their own authentic values. Teachers observed that students were open, reflective, and willing to share personal experiences. They particularly appreciated the balanced mix of discussion and visual content from the presentation, which made the topic relatable and easy to understand. The activity encouraged mutual respect and empathy among students and opened important classroom dialogue about self-image, comparison, and the meaning of success.

The sessions with preadolescents showed that the *Role Models* learning unit effectively raises awareness about values, authenticity, and personal responsibility, helping students recognize how media and everyday experiences shape their understanding of themselves and others.

Pilot with parents

Workshops for parents were held in all three schools in December 2024, each lasting around 60 minutes and attended by 101 participants in total. The goal was to familiarise parents with the activities carried out with children and to open a dialogue about the impact of influencers and digital media on children's self-perception. Facilitators presented examples from the classroom and discussed with parents how online trends and social comparison affect children's mood, motivation and self-esteem.

Parents expressed strong interest and appreciation for the topic, noting that this was one of the most relevant and useful workshops they had attended. Many shared that they often feel uncertain about how to talk with their children about social media and influencers, and they welcomed the practical guidance and examples provided.

In their evaluation, parents emphasized that such workshops should be offered more frequently and that they would like to continue joint sessions involving both parents and children.

Pilot with teachers

A series of sessions for teachers involved a total of 78 teachers. Session lasted about 60 minutes and combined presentation, discussion, and peer reflection. Teachers reviewed the *Role Models* learning materials and discussed how to apply them in different subjects and class contexts. They appreciated that the materials were easy to integrate into regular lessons without requiring extensive preparation, allowing teachers to address important topics even with limited time. In their reflections, teachers noted that this learning unit helps students develop critical thinking, emotional awareness, and resilience against unrealistic social-media standards.

As one teacher commented: “Students often idolize influencers who promote superficial success. These activities give us a way to talk about real values, kindness, honesty, and effort in a language students understand.”

Another added: “What I like most is that I can use it tomorrow, in any class. It doesn’t need complicated setup; it just opens up meaningful discussion.”

Teachers agreed that such lessons are essential in modern education, as they provide students with tools to question digital pressures and form authentic, balanced identities.

Conclusion

Pilot 2 confirmed the strong relevance and practical impact of the *Role Models* learning unit. The activities successfully encouraged preadolescents to question online influences and to identify personal values that matter beyond digital appearance. Parents appreciated learning how to talk about these topics at home, while teachers valued the simplicity and adaptability of the materials, which can be applied across subjects and age groups.

The pilot demonstrated that discussions about role models are a powerful way to strengthen students’ critical thinking, emotional resilience, and self-esteem in the digital age. Future implementation should continue to include parents as active partners and provide more opportunities for joint reflection between families and schools.

2.3. Pilot 3

General introduction to the pilot

Pilot 3 was conducted from April to June 2025 in cooperation with partner schools across Croatia, primarily in Zagreb, Samobor and Krapina. A total of 752 participants took part, including 389 preadolescents, 63 teachers and 291 parents.

Unlike the previous phases, during this stage schools were given the freedom to choose the learning units most relevant to their students’ needs. As a result, different schools implemented activities from the *Emotions*, *Communication*, *Role Models*, and *Onlife* learning units. This flexible approach allowed educators to respond to the specific challenges observed among their students, such as emotional regulation, online behaviour, peer pressure and digital well-being. The main objective of this phase was to evaluate the scalability and adaptability of the ASAP Educational Programme across diverse school contexts and to assess how trained educators could independently implement the activities.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

Nineteen interactive sessions with preadolescents (aged 12–13) were carried out between April and June 2025 in several schools (Primary School Odra, Primary School Josipa Račića, Primary School Samobor, Primary school Krapina and Primary School Ivana Cankara).

Altogether, 389 students participated. The selected activities were drawn from the Learning Units *Emotions* and *Communication*, and some schools also incorporated elements from *Role Models* and *Onlife* depending on their students' interests and needs. The sessions aimed to encourage reflection on how emotions, communication, and values influence online behaviour.

Activities such as Bingo and Emoji stories from the *Emotions* unit helped students recognise emotions triggered by social media interactions and learn how to respond thoughtfully rather than impulsively. From the *Communication* unit, activities on Active Listening and I-Messages exercises were implemented, allowing students to explore different communication styles, passive, aggressive and assertive and to practise expressing their opinions respectfully. In several schools, teachers combined these lessons with role models and personal values. Students were invited to think about who influences their attitudes and choices, and which personal values they consider most important.

Feedback collected through pen-and-paper surveys and short group reflections showed high engagement and positive emotional response. Students particularly enjoyed interactive and playful methods and group discussions about real-life online experiences. Many reported that it was easier to express feelings “through games” than through direct conversation, and that these activities helped them better understand their emotions and how to react in online situations.

Teachers observed that students became more aware of the impact of their words and online actions and that many started to connect classroom discussions with their daily digital interactions. As one teacher summarised, “Many kids are quick to react but slow to listen. These activities help slow things down and make them think before they act.” The sessions demonstrated that when given space for reflection and expression, students can develop greater empathy, emotional self-regulation, and more respectful communication skills. The combination of creative exercises, discussion, and media examples proved highly effective in engaging preadolescents and supporting their emotional and social development in the digital age.

Pilot with parents

Nine 60-minute workshops for parents were conducted from April to June 2025 in several partner schools, gathering 291 parents in total. The workshops incorporated findings from classroom activities and addressed the key challenges observed among preadolescents, such as excessive screen time, participation in online challenges, lack of awareness of online risks, and emotional impulsivity in digital spaces. Parents were invited to reflect on their children's online experiences and their own communication habits at home.

Through role play and practical examples, parents explored how to talk with their children about online behaviour, how to set healthy boundaries, and how to model positive digital habits. They discussed real situations shared by students such as sharing photos they later regret, reacting to social media pressure, or taking part in viral challenges without understanding the consequences. The facilitators also presented examples of cyberbullying scenarios, explaining that many children do not perceive such actions as harmful but rather as fun. Parents learned to recognise different forms of online aggression (offensive messages, exclusion from chats, spreading rumours, sharing

embarrassing photos or videos) and how to react calmly and supportively if such issues arise. A particularly valuable part of the session focused on the digital footprint helping parents understand that everything shared online leaves a trace. Facilitators shared simple messages they can use at home. Parents also discussed the use of phones before bedtime, as many students reported sleep problems related to late-night device use. Practical suggestions were offered for establishing family offline time.

Throughout the workshop, the atmosphere was interactive, open, and supportive. Parents appreciated the practical examples, the realistic portrayal of children's online experiences, and the opportunity to exchange ideas with other parents. Many expressed that they had never talked about these topics so openly before and that the session helped them feel more confident in guiding their children through digital challenges.

In their feedback, parents highlighted that they greatly enjoyed the workshop and requested that more sessions like this be organised in the future. They particularly valued the balance between theory and practice, saying it helped them better understand the world their children live in and gave them concrete tools for positive communication, conflict resolution, and emotional support. The parent workshops in Pilot 3 proved to be a key step toward strengthening collaboration between families and schools and building a shared understanding of healthy, safe and empathetic digital behaviour.

Pilot with teachers

A series of sessions for teachers were organised between April and June 2025, involving a total of 63 teachers from several partner schools. Session lasted around 60 minutes and combined presentation, discussion, and peer reflection. Teachers reviewed and tested activities from different Learning Units, primarily *Communication*, *Emotions* and *Onlife*, reflecting on how they could be integrated into everyday classroom work.

The sessions provided space for teachers to exchange experiences and discuss how emotional education, communication skill, and empathy can support a positive classroom atmosphere and student well-being. They appreciated that the activities are simple, flexible, and directly applicable, requiring minimal preparation and easily fitting into various subjects such as homeroom classes, ethics or civic education. Teachers emphasised that the lessons help students develop empathy, improve mutual understanding, and communicate more respectfully, both online and offline. Many noted that these topics are becoming increasingly important in schools, as students often struggle with emotional regulation and constructive communication.

As one teacher explained: "These lessons remind us that communication and empathy are the basis of everything, learning, friendship, and even how students behave online." Another added: "What I like most is that all these activities can be used immediately in class. They help students think, talk, and listen to each other in a safe way."

Teachers agreed that all learning units, especially *Communication* and *Emotions*, are highly relevant and complementary, promoting not only digital awareness but also social and emotional growth. They concluded that such programmes strengthen both students' interpersonal skills and the overall classroom climate, making learning more inclusive and supportive.

Conclusion

Pilot 3 confirmed the feasibility, scalability, and long-term value of the ASAP Educational Programme in Croatia. Conducted across multiple partner schools and facilitated by trained educators, the pilot demonstrated that the programme can be successfully integrated into everyday school life with strong engagement from students, parents, and teachers. Across all activities, participants showed greater emotional awareness, improved communication skills, and stronger empathy, both in digital interactions and face-to-face relationships. The flexible approach, which allowed schools to choose the most relevant learning units proved highly effective in meeting the specific needs of different student groups.

The pilot showed that the combination of emotional education and digital citizenship creates a meaningful foundation for positive behavioural change and healthier online culture in schools. Key recommendations for future implementation include extending workshop duration to allow more time for discussion and reflection, continuing to develop joint sessions for parents and children to strengthen home–school cooperation, providing ongoing support and peer exchange opportunities for teachers to share good practices and maintaining flexibility in learning unit selection while ensuring consistent educational outcomes.

Pilot 3 demonstrated that the ASAP Educational Programme can be effectively scaled within Croatian schools, fostering empathy, emotional intelligence, and responsible digital citizenship, skills essential for both learning and life.

Overall conclusion for Croatia

Across the three pilot phases in Croatia, a total of over 1,222 participants including preadolescents, parents, and teachers took part in structured activities focusing on the learning units Emotions, Communication, Role Models, and Onlife. The pilots successfully validated the relevance, flexibility, and adaptability of the ASAP Educational Programme to Croatian school and family contexts.

Participants consistently praised the interactive, practical and relatable nature of the materials. The activities encouraged open dialogue, reflection, and emotional expression, while supporting the development of empathy, critical thinking and responsible online behaviour. Both teachers and parents recognised the value of these lessons for strengthening relationships, improving communication, and helping children better navigate their online and offline worlds.

A particularly positive outcome of the Croatian implementation was the high level of interest and motivation among schools to participate in the ASAP pilots. Many schools expressed willingness to continue using the learning units in regular curricula and extracurricular activities, viewing them as a valuable contribution to promoting emotional well-being and digital citizenship. Key takeaways highlight the need for more detailed facilitation guidelines and follow-up support for teachers, longer sessions to allow deeper reflection and discussion and further development of joint parent–child workshops to strengthen home–school collaboration.

The Croatian pilots clearly confirmed that the ASAP Educational Programme is an effective, engaging and contextually appropriate tool for fostering empathy, emotional literacy and responsible digital behaviour among preadolescents, while also building stronger connections between schools, families and the wider community.

3. Czech Republic

The national piloting of the ASAP Educational Programme in the Czech Republic was carried out by ProEduca in close collaboration with local schools, teachers, and parents. The main goal was to test and adapt the programme’s learning units to the Czech educational context and to evaluate their effectiveness in supporting emotional literacy, authentic communication, and responsible digital behaviour among preadolescents.

The piloting was implemented in three consecutive phases between 2024 and 2025, gradually expanding in scope and participation. Altogether, the Czech piloting involved 1566 participants, including 745 preadolescents, 262 teachers, 33 school leaders and 537 parents. All six learning units — *Emotions, Communication, Authenticity, Power of Questions, Role Models, and Onlife* — were tested across all phases, ensuring a comprehensive validation of the educational framework.

The implementation confirmed that the programme is highly relevant, engaging, and applicable to Czech schools. Teachers and parents expressed a strong interest in integrating its activities into regular curricula, emphasising that the combination of emotional and digital literacy directly supports students’ well-being and personal development.

3.1. Pilot 1

The first pilot phase in the Czech Republic was implemented between March and April 2024 in cooperation with one primary school in the South Bohemian region. The implementation engaged a total of 143 participants, including 70 preadolescents, 11 teachers, 2 school leaders and 60 parents.

The activities selected for this phase were drawn from the Learning Unit “Emotions”, focusing on developing emotional awareness, empathy, and self-regulation both online and offline. This first testing phase aimed to verify the clarity of the learning materials, assess the age-appropriateness of activities, and evaluate the facilitation process from both the teacher’s and student’s perspectives.

Sessions were delivered in small classroom groups by facilitators who had participated in the internal partner training. The pilot explored how preadolescents recognise, express, and manage emotions in digital communication, and how parents and teachers can support this process.

The implementation of Pilot 1 provided valuable insight into how Czech students perceive emotions in the digital environment and how easily they can connect classroom discussions to their own online experiences. Despite its limited scale, the pilot successfully demonstrated the emotional relevance and engagement potential of the activities.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

The activities with students were implemented in two local schools, involving 70 preadolescents aged 11–13. Each group participated in one 45-minute session, focused on recognising emotions, expressing them appropriately, and understanding their role in digital communication.

Activities such as “On question”, “Emoji” and “Bingo” were particularly successful in sparking student interest. Students actively shared examples from social media, discussed moments when online comments or emojis were misunderstood, and reflected on the impact of emotions on their behaviour. Facilitators noted that once the activities became playful, students opened up and engaged in surprisingly mature reflections about empathy, online anger, and self-control.

Verbal feedback gathered at the end of sessions showed that most students found the workshops “fun” and “different from usual lessons.” They appreciated that they could talk freely about social media and emotions in a safe environment.

Teachers who observed the sessions reported that students were more focused and cooperative than expected and that the format encouraged open discussion even among quieter pupils.

Pilot with parents

A series of 45-minute workshops for parents was organised to present the same activities as piloted with the kids, but with the focus on adults’ perspective. The sessions were attended by 60 parents in total, many of them came repeatedly for different activities.

Parents were introduced to the concepts of emotional triggers in online communication, empathy in digital spaces, and strategies for supporting emotional balance in their children’s online life. Discussion revolved around the difference between parental control and guidance, with several participants sharing examples from their own family experience.

Parents expressed that the session helped them better understand what their children encounter online and how to react to emotional conflicts that originate in digital environments. Many highlighted that they appreciated seeing their children’s learning process and requested that more workshops of this kind be organised at school.

Pilot with teachers

A separate workshop for 11 teachers and 2 school leaders was conducted to run the same activities also with educators, have them experience them, review the materials and discuss their classroom applicability. The teachers went through selected activities from the *Emotions* unit, analysing possible adaptations for different age groups and subjects.

The overall response was highly positive. Teachers described the activities as creative, ready-to-use, and easy to integrate into lessons such as civic education, homeroom classes, or preventive programmes. Several pointed out that the structure of the lessons encourages emotional reflection and peer understanding—elements they often miss in traditional teaching materials.

Teachers also noted that emotional education is a growing need in Czech schools, as many students struggle with impulsive reactions, frustration, and emotional overexposure due to social media. The materials were seen as a much-needed bridge between academic and emotional learning.

Conclusion

Pilot 1 confirmed that the Emotions learning unit is suitable and effective for Czech primary school students. It successfully engaged children, parents, and teachers alike and demonstrated that emotional awareness is a crucial skill for the digital generation.

The pilot also showed that Czech teachers are ready and motivated to address these topics, provided they receive well-structured materials and facilitation guidance. Participants collectively agreed that emotional literacy should become part of the regular educational offer, helping students reflect on how emotions shape their behaviour both online and offline.

Key recommendations from the first pilot include providing more time for discussion, offering a short facilitation guide for teachers, and developing additional follow-up activities that help maintain emotional awareness in daily classroom life.

3.2. Pilot 2

The second piloting phase of the ASAP Educational Programme in the Czech Republic took place between October 2024 and January 2025. Building on the first pilot, which focused primarily on emotional literacy, this phase expanded the testing to include activities from all Learning Units: *Emotions, Communication, Authenticity, Power of Questions, Role Models, and Onlife*.

A total of 271 participants were engaged, including 136 preadolescents, 23 teachers, 2 school leaders and 110 parents. The activities were implemented in cooperation with three local schools that had previously participated in the project's preparatory phase. The sessions were facilitated both by teachers and by ProEduca trainers, ensuring a mix of guided and independently led implementations.

The purpose of this second phase was to assess how well the full set of learning units functioned in practice and to observe how preadolescents respond when the activities are sequenced together rather than as isolated exercises. Schools were encouraged to select and adapt activities according to their current educational priorities and time constraints, creating a flexible yet structured learning experience.

Overall, the second pilot confirmed the consistency, adaptability, and engagement potential of the ASAP methodology. It showed that the programme can function effectively in diverse classroom settings, supporting both digital literacy and social-emotional learning in a balanced and complementary way.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

The pilot activities were implemented with twelve groups of students, reaching a total of 136 preadolescents. Each group participated in two to three sessions, usually 45 minutes long, integrated into civic education, homeroom, or thematic project days.

The sequence of topics followed a simple progression: starting with *Emotions* and *Communication* to build trust and understanding, continuing with *Authenticity* and *Role Models* to reflect on personal identity and influences, and concluding with *Power of Questions* and *Onlife* to stimulate critical thinking about digital behaviour.

Students particularly enjoyed activities that combined playfulness and reflection — such as Emoji Bingo, but also activities from another learning units, such as: Exploring values in our lives, Viral challenge match-up, My digital footprint, Active listening, Walk in someone else's shoes. These tasks encouraged self-expression, cooperation, and real-life connections to their own online experiences.

Teachers noted that students became more engaged when they were given space to express opinions and emotions freely. Many commented that these topics are highly relevant, as pupils often struggle to discuss feelings or online pressures openly in traditional lessons. The interactive and game-like format of ASAP made such discussions natural and enjoyable.

Facilitators collected feedback orally at the end of sessions. Most students described the lessons as “interesting,” “different,” and “helpful.” Some said that they now think more before reacting online

or posting comments, while others admitted that they had recognised their own behaviour in the examples.

Pilot with parents

Twelve interactive 60-minute workshops for parents were held during the second pilot phase, gathering 110 participants. The workshops aimed to familiarise parents with what their children were learning – more or less the very same set of activities - and also provided space to encourage reflection on digital boundaries, family communication, and the emotional side of online life.

The sessions covered topics such as:

- How emotions influence communication online and offline.
- The role of parental example in shaping children’s online habits.
- Constructive dialogue about social media use and peer influence.

Parents appreciated the practical tone of the workshops and valued the opportunity to exchange experiences with others. Several participants admitted that they were surprised by how complex and emotionally charged the digital world is for their children. They particularly liked the simplicity of the materials and how easily the same principles could be applied at home.

The overall feedback was highly positive: parents expressed a wish for the workshops to be repeated and extended to include both children and parents together. Many remarked that the project helped open conversations that had previously been avoided in the family.

Pilot with teachers

A total of 23 teachers participated in the second pilot phase, attending review sessions and classroom trials. Each school organised at least one internal workshop where teachers discussed facilitation experiences and proposed minor adjustments to the materials.

Teachers agreed that the combination of emotional and digital literacy is particularly valuable in today’s classrooms. They appreciated that the materials required minimal preparation, were visually attractive, and could be flexibly adapted for different lesson lengths.

Several teachers highlighted that ASAP activities can serve as a unifying tool across school prevention programmes, class community-building, and digital education. One teacher commented that “these lessons finally give us a language to talk about emotions, online risks, and values in one coherent flow.”

The reflection meetings confirmed that teachers found the materials useful, meaningful, and easy to replicate. They suggested that future editions could include even more examples from Czech schools to make them locally relatable, but otherwise expressed strong satisfaction and motivation to continue using the programme.

Conclusion

Pilot 2 demonstrated the internal coherence and pedagogical versatility of the ASAP Educational Programme. By testing all six learning units, Czech schools confirmed that the materials work effectively both as stand-alone lessons and as a connected learning journey.

Students showed high engagement, parents valued the insight into their children’s online world, and teachers emphasised the programme’s practical relevance. Across all groups, participants appreciated the focus on empathy, critical thinking, and authentic communication—skills that support both academic success and personal well-being.

The main recommendation emerging from this pilot was to maintain the flexibility of the programme while providing teachers with brief implementation guidelines to ensure consistency. Schools also expressed strong interest in formally integrating the ASAP lessons into the national curriculum, particularly within civic education and preventive programmes.

3.3. Pilot 3

The third and final piloting phase of the ASAP Educational Programme in the Czech Republic took place between February and May 2025 in cooperation with several partner schools in the South Bohemian region. This phase was split into 2 parts: Pilot 3A engaged a total of 707 participants, including 334 preadolescents, 119 teachers, 8 school leaders, and 246 parents. Pilot 3B engaged a total of 445 participants, including 205 preadolescents, 109 teachers, 10 school leaders and 121 parents.

Unlike the previous stages, which focused on selected activities, the third pilot tested the complete set of all Learning Units – *Emotions, Communication, Authenticity, Power of Questions, Role Models, and Onlife*. The objective was to verify the programme’s internal coherence, identify possible overlaps between learning units, and assess the programme’s long-term usability as an integrated framework for emotional and digital literacy education.

The implementation involved both classroom activities and joint reflection sessions with teachers. Each participating school was encouraged to adapt the sessions according to its own timetable and student needs. This flexibility made it possible to test a wide range of facilitation formats – from short 45-minute blocks to half-day workshops and thematic days.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

A total of 539 preadolescents participated in the sessions. Activities were implemented by trained teachers who had already been involved in previous pilot phases. Building on earlier experience, the facilitators adjusted the order of topics to create a logical progression: starting with *Emotions* and *Communication* to establish trust and self-awareness, followed by *Authenticity* and *Role Models* to foster reflection on identity, and concluding with *Power of Questions* and *Onlife* to encourage critical thinking and responsible online behaviour.

The students responded enthusiastically to the diversity of activities, especially those involving storytelling, group movement, and creative exercises. Among the most appreciated tasks were “Mapping my Onlife,” “Anatomy of a news story”, “I-Messages,” “How information shapes our views” and “Similarities and differences between traditional and digital role models”. These activities encouraged spontaneous participation and peer interaction while keeping discussions grounded in real experiences.

Teachers observed that by this stage, students had grown significantly more reflective compared to the first pilot. They were able to link earlier lessons to new insights – for example, identifying how emotions influence communication or how authenticity relates to online self-presentation. Facilitators

noted visible progress in empathy and self-expression, as many students started to use more balanced language and became more attentive listeners.

Although no formal evaluation sheets were used, informal feedback collected during final reflections showed very positive responses. Many students described the activities as “something every class should do,” adding that they appreciated being treated “like equals” when discussing serious online topics.

Pilot with parents

A series of interactive workshops for 367 parents in total were held in participating schools between March and May 2025. The aim was to share the children’s learning experience – during the same kind of activities - and provide parents with practical tools to support healthy digital habits at home.

Sessions combined short presentations, video examples, and discussion. Parents reflected on topics such as emotional regulation, online safety, and the influence of role models. They also learned about communication techniques used in the programme (e.g. “I-Messages,” “Active Listening”) and how to apply them in family situations.

The atmosphere of the sessions was open and collaborative. Parents expressed gratitude that schools addressed these topics and shared that they found it easier to start conversations with their children after the workshops. Some commented that they recognised similar emotional reactions in themselves when using digital media, which made the experience even more relevant.

Overall, parents highlighted the importance of continuing such sessions regularly and expressed clear support for including the ASAP programme as part of the official school curriculum.

Pilot with teachers

A total of 228 teachers participated in reflection and testing sessions during the final phase. They reviewed the full set of activities and provided comments on the practical use of materials across different age groups and subjects. All groups of teachers went through all the planned activities, tested them on themselves and also applied them in their own lessons when possible.

Teachers appreciated that the structure of the learning units is modular and adaptable, allowing them to select activities that fit their teaching goals. They found the content particularly valuable for homeroom classes, prevention programmes, and thematic projects related to digital citizenship and social-emotional learning.

Most teachers reported that the ASAP activities had a visible positive effect on classroom climate. Students were calmer, more empathetic, and more willing to cooperate during discussions. Teachers also observed improved conflict resolution and greater self-awareness among students who had participated in multiple units.

In their informal feedback, teachers described the materials as “modern, meaningful, and realistic.” Several noted that these sessions helped them build stronger relationships with students and provided new ways to discuss sensitive online topics without judgement or moralising.

Conclusion

The third pilot phase confirmed the completeness, scalability, and long-term potential of the ASAP Educational Programme. Conducted across several schools with participants from all target groups, it demonstrated that the methodology works effectively in different educational settings and can be integrated into daily teaching practice with minimal adaptation.

Teachers and parents alike expressed a strong wish for the programme to become a permanent component of school curricula – either as part of personal and social education, or as an interdisciplinary module linked to digital citizenship and emotional well-being.

Students showed tangible progress in empathy, critical thinking, and emotional self-regulation. Teachers reported increased peer respect and more responsible online behaviour among participants.

The Czech pilot clearly demonstrated that when emotional education and digital literacy are combined, they create a powerful foundation for resilience, empathy, and responsible digital presence. The overall success of the third pilot provides a strong argument for sustaining and institutionalising the ASAP methodology in Czech schools.

4. Portugal

The national piloting of the ASAP Educational Programme in Portugal was conducted by COFAC - Lusófona University, an educational institution specialised in higher education and research. The pilot was conducted in close collaboration with local schools, and its main goal was to test and adapt the programme's learning units to the Portuguese formal education context. The pilot also intended to evaluate the effectiveness of the learning units and activities in supporting emotional literacy, authentic communication, and responsible digital behaviour among preadolescents.

Piloting was conducted in three phases between November 2024 and May 2025. Altogether, the Portuguese pilot involved 159 participants: 25 teachers, 1 school leader, and 133 students. The pilot focused mainly on three learning units: Emotions, Onlife, and Authenticity. These were tested across the various phases to validate the educational framework.

Furthermore, the Pilot conducted in Portugal had one of its priorities a significant focus on emotions, communication, and social-media-related challenges and topics, which are highly relevant to preadolescents, families and also schools and that tend to be absent from regular discussions within educational contexts, particularly from the point of view of students as active agents in their own learning.

The results of the implementation reveal that the ASAP programme is appropriate, engaging, and applicable to Portuguese schools. Both teachers and students expressed interest in integrating its activities into regular curricula as well as extracurricular activities, stressing that the combination of socio-technological topics - particularly emotional and digital literacy - supports students' well-being, personal and professional development.

4.1. Pilot 1

The first pilot phase was implemented in November 2024 in two private schools in Northern Portugal. Both schools offered education from preschool to secondary school. This phase of implementation engaged 39 students and two teachers - English and Mathematics.

The activities tested during this phase were drawn from the Learning Unit "Emotions", which focused on developing emotional awareness, empathy, and self-regulation both online and offline. This first phase aimed to verify the clarity of the learning materials, assess the age appropriateness of the activities, and evaluate the facilitation process from both the teacher's and the student's perspectives.

Sessions were delivered with two classes of students, one with 23 students (7th grade) and one with 16 students (8th grade), accompanied by their respective teachers. The pilot explored how preadolescents recognise, express, and manage emotions in digital communication, and how teachers can play an active role in supporting this process.

Pilot 1 provided fundamental insights into how Portuguese students and teachers perceive emotions in the digital environment and how activities about these topics can be integrated into several curricular units. Despite the pilot's limited scale, it was successfully implemented and demonstrated the relevance of the Learning Unit and its activities.

The activities implemented with the two groups of students and teachers during this first pilot were "Emoji" and "Post-its". Both activities sparked students' interest and stimulated collective discussion and reflection on issues related to online emotions and the emotional impacts of social media and online contexts. Although it is clear that not all participants engage with the same level of interest and motivation, the activities also demonstrated that they fulfilled their purpose of promoting engaging group collaborations. It should be noted that its playful and entertaining nature also created opportunities for students to gradually open up about their personal experiences and anxieties regarding the topic at hand. The discussions revealed a level of interest and concern about the topics, indicating an awareness of the importance of raising them for discussion.

At the end of each session, verbal feedback was collected. It showed that most students and teachers enjoyed the approach and the activities, describing them as different and as new spaces to reflect on social media and emotions.

All in all, Pilot 1 demonstrated that the Emotions learning unit successfully supports preadolescents' emotional intelligence and digital well-being, while providing teachers with new tools to incorporate these topics in the classroom. Recommendations that arose from this pilot mainly relate to the duration of the sessions, which, with some groups, might be extended to achieve better results, as well as to amplify the guidance teachers and facilitators provide on these topics.

4.2. Pilot 2

Pilot 2 was implemented in November 2025 in three schools in northern Portugal. The pilot engaged 56 students, 3 teachers and 1 school leader.

The activities tested during this phase were drawn from the Onlife Learning Unit, designed to help students critically reflect on the boundaries between the physical and digital worlds and the impacts of behaviours in digital contexts on experiences in the physical world. Through interactive exercises and guided discussions, participants explored how to navigate these interconnected worlds responsibly, ensuring that their online actions reflect the values learned in formal and informal settings.

The implementation of Pilot 2 offered crucial insights into how preadolescents understand their online experiences, how these experiences impact their physical experiences, and how teachers can support them towards greater self-awareness, independence, and emotional resilience.

Each group of students participated in one 45-minute session, integrated into Civic Education, Mathematics, and English curricular units. The sequence of topics/activities followed a simple progression: starting with a critical reflection on their *Digital Footprint*, students then engaged in the *Reverse play* or the *Onlife mapping activity*.

Students revealed multiple feelings. On the one hand, students initially found it challenging to think about their digital footprint and all the spaces where they leave traces of their online experiences and activities; on the other hand, once involved in the dynamics of the learning unit, they demonstrated an ability for in-depth reflection and a set of advanced digital knowledge and skills (e.g., knowledge of cookies, future impacts of digital footprints). These tasks encouraged self-expression, cooperation, and real-life connections in their own online experiences.

As for teachers, the oral feedback collected after each session showed that they appreciated the activities, flexible structures, and opportunities across various subjects.

Facilitators collected feedback at the end of the sessions. Regarding the activities implemented during Pilot 2, students particularly described the lessons as "fun" and "different". A few mentioned that in the future they would think more carefully about their online actions and activities, reflecting on possible future impacts.

Pilot 2 confirmed the current pertinence and practical impact of the *Onlife* learning unit. The activities successfully encouraged preadolescents to question the online actions and their physical-life implications. Teachers appreciated new tools and approaches for integrating these topics into curricula across different subjects.

Future implementation should provide more opportunities for joint reflection between families and schools, as well as varying levels of depth that allow students, teachers, and even families to deepen their knowledge of onlife dynamics, the influence of algorithms, and the impacts of the citizenship experience.

4.3. Pilot 3

The third piloting phase of the ASAP Educational Programme in Portugal took place between April and May 2025 in cooperation with one school in Northern Portugal. It was split into two sessions, with groups of 19 students and 1 teacher each.

During this stage, schools chose the learning unit most relevant to their students' needs. During a discussion with one school leader of the institution, it became clear that the Emotions Learning Unit will be the most relevant to implement with the selected group of students. Topics such as emotional regulation in online contexts were of particular interest. The main goal of this phase was to evaluate the scalability and adaptability of the ASAP Educational Programme to assess how trained educators could independently implement the activities. Therefore, the teachers assumed a more active role in dynamising the activities.

The implementation involved classroom activities and final reflections with teachers. Each group was encouraged to propose adaptations before each pilot session based on its students' needs. This flexibility enabled testing different facilitation formats and possible adaptations to the activities themselves.

The activities selected by the teachers who attended the sessions were Emoji, Post-its, Short Video, and Moodboard. According to the teachers, these activities would be most appropriate for the student groups and address their emotional needs and their lack of digital skills and knowledge.

The Emoji, Post-its, Short Video, and Moodboard activities helped students recognise emotions triggered by social media interactions and learn how to respond thoughtfully rather than impulsively. The activities also achieved their goal of sparking discussions about the overall impact of social media and digital contexts on relationships with peers, friends, and adults.

Feedback collected after each session showed high engagement. As teachers played a key role in implementing classroom activities, it was possible to assess the general willingness of students and teachers to discuss their emotions and online experiences openly. Both teachers and students reported that it was easier to express feelings through games and play than through direct conversation. Therefore, the activities helped them better understand their emotions and how to react in online situations.

Teachers expressed confidence in implementing the activities and were able to link them to their subjects—in this case, Citizenship Education. In their opinion, the proposed activities and general learning unit can be easily integrated into the annual activity plan for the Citizenship Education subject. The sessions demonstrated that when given space for reflection and expression, students can develop greater empathy and respectful communication skills towards others. By combining creative exercises with discussion and media examples, the activities proved effective in engaging preadolescents and teachers through thoughtful and profound reflections on emotional development and social relations.

5. Slovenia

Pilots in Slovenia were implemented at two primary schools: Osnovna šola Janka Padežnika Maribor, which also participated as associated partner in the ASAP project, and Osnovna šola Angela Besednjaka Maribor. The overall objective of pilot implementation was to disseminate the project results, influence the attitudes and behaviours of the target groups and to test the clarity and feasibility of the selected learning units and their respective activities.

In pilot 1, we reached 78 participants (the plan was 76), in pilot 2 75 participants (the plan was 76) and in pilot 3 349 participants (the plan was 185). Therefore, we reached in total 597 participants (the plan was 468).

5.1. Pilot 1

General introduction to the pilot

Pilot 1 was implemented at Osnovna šola Janka Padežnika Maribor in June 2024 and January 2025. In total, 78 participants were involved in pilot 1: 40 preadolescent, 31 parents, 6 teachers and 1 school leader. Selected activities of the Learning unit Emotions were implemented and tested.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

Two sessions with preadolescents were implemented targeting in total 40 participants (20 in each class). Their age range was 11-12. The sessions were conducted in June 2024, each lasting 45 minutes. The first session addressed the Bingo learning activity, and the second session addressed the Emoji and Post-it-notes activities.

The Bingo activity was adapted to fit a 45-minute school session and used as a standalone exercise to spark discussion on online habits and risky digital behaviours. Trainers shortened the discussion to maintain focus and adjusted instructions for time efficiency. The learning activities Emoji and Post-it notes were also adapted by merging them into a single 45-minute session, focused on communication and emotional expression. The trainers simplified the discussion to fit the limited time and adjusted facilitation to keep preadolescents engaged.

The feedback was collected by pen-and-paper surveys administered at the end of each session. The Bingo activity was engaging and well-received, with most students enjoying the interactive format and its relevance to online behaviour. However, sustaining attention during reflection proved challenging, and some participants felt uncomfortable revealing personal information. Clearer facilitation guidelines and a privacy-sensitive variation (e.g., signing for someone they know rather than themselves) were recommended. Overall, the activity was rated positively for likeability and usefulness.

The Emoji and Post-it-notes activities were also engaging and well-received, especially the emoji guessing and compliment exchanges, but maintaining focus during discussions was challenging. Facilitators noted the need for clearer, more detailed instructions and stronger discussion prompts. Overall, the workshop was rated positively for likeability and usefulness, though improvements were suggested to make examples more relevant and discussions more structured.

Pilot with parents

One session with parents was implemented targeting in total 31 participants. The session was conducted in January 2025, lasting nearly 30 minutes. The Bingo and Emoji activities were tested.

Both activities were merged, shortened and adapted to fit in the frame of 30 minutes. Parents reviewed the list of activities specified in the Bingo card and specified, which were valid for them. Then, they tried to guess the meaning of sentences written by emojis and were involved in the wrap-up discussion to convey the key messages.

The feedback was collected by online survey administered at the end of the session. The evaluation shows that participants found the workshop very positive, useful, and worth recommending to other parents. They especially appreciated the practical examples, short and clear activities, and the engaging, interactive approach. The main suggestion for improvement was to allow more time and include additional examples or follow-up workshops, ideally involving children as well. Overall, the workshop was seen as relevant, effective, and a valuable learning experience.

Pilot with teachers

The pilot with teachers was conducted as a one-hour workshop involving 6 teachers and 1 school principal (June 2024). Instead of directly carrying out the learning activities, facilitators presented and explained each one—its purpose, implementation, and key messages—and gathered teachers' feedback on clarity, usefulness, and feasibility. The following learning activities were tested and evaluated: Questions (with pictures), Bingo, Emoji, Post-it-notes.

The feedback was collected verbally throughout the discussion and by pen-and-paper survey administered at the end of the session. Teachers found the activities engaging and relevant for addressing online behaviour and emotions but emphasized the need for clearer, more detailed facilitation instructions and examples. They suggested shortening some tasks, rephrasing vague questions, and providing structured discussion prompts to help guide reflection. The Bingo and Emoji/Post-it-notes activities were seen as particularly useful starting points for exploring online safety and emotional awareness, though they would benefit from stronger guidance on sequencing and classroom management. Teachers proposed organizing the activities into a condensed "activity day" format and developing a clearer implementation timeline. They also agreed that most activities could be suitable for parents, except the "Questions" activity, which might be too personal.

Conclusion

Pilot 1, implemented at Osnovna šola Janka Padežnika Maribor with 78 participants, confirmed that the "Emotions" learning activities are engaging, relevant, and adaptable across preadolescents, parents, and teachers. All groups appreciated the interactive and practical nature of the sessions, particularly the Bingo and Emoji/Post-it-notes activities. However, participants and facilitators highlighted the need for clearer, more detailed guidance, stronger discussion prompts, and slightly more time for reflection. Teachers also suggested a condensed "activity day" format and improved sequencing between activities. Overall, the pilot demonstrated strong educational value and provided concrete directions for refining materials and facilitation support.

5.2. Pilot 2

General introduction to the pilot

Pilot 2 was implemented at Osnovna šola Janka Padežnika Maribor in the period January – May 2025. In total, 75 participants were involved in pilot 2: 40 preadolescent, 29 parents and 6 teachers and 1 school leader. Selected activities of the learning units Communication and Onlife were implemented and tested.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

Two sessions with preadolescents were implemented targeting in total 40 participants (20 in each class). Their age range was 10-11. The sessions were conducted in January 2025, each lasting 45 minutes. The first session addressed the activity 2.a.1 of the Communication learning unit (exploring different response styles), and the second session addressed the activity 2.a.2 of the Communication learning unit (recognising the response style and proposing an alternative). No major adaptations of the proposed learning activities were required.

The feedback was collected by pen-and-paper surveys administered at the end of each session. Preadolescents generally found the activity 2.a.1 (exploring different response styles) interesting and useful. Preadolescents most appreciated that the session encouraged open and meaningful conversation about different response styles (passive, assertive, and aggressive behaviour). They valued being able to share real-life experiences, discuss concrete examples, and engage in a deeper dialogue than usual. The atmosphere was described as friendly and supportive, with teachers explaining situations clearly and respectfully. Overall, students enjoyed the interactive, open, and relatable discussion, which made the topic feel relevant and educational.

Preadolescents generally liked the activity 2.a.2 and considered it useful. Preadolescents most appreciated the collaborative group work and the opportunity to discuss and learn through communication. They enjoyed working together with classmates, sharing opinions, and reflecting on different types of behaviour. Many noted that the session helped them recognize whether their own actions were appropriate and understand various response styles. Overall, they valued the interactive, discussion-based approach, which made learning about behaviour and communication both engaging and meaningful. Some of them considered the session as too short and would appreciate to have more time devoted for such activities.

Pilot with parents

A session with parents was conducted in March 2025, involving a total of 29 participants. The session, lasting approximately 60 minutes, focused on the learning unit Communication and included the implementation and testing of three activities: Active Listening, Different Response Styles (2.a.1), and I-Messages (2.b.1).

To fit within the available time, all activities were merged, shortened, and adapted. The Active Listening activity was fully modified, with two facilitators demonstrating both active and non-active listening and engaging parents in a discussion that followed. The activity on Different Response Styles (2.a.1) was implemented briefly, while there was too little time for the full implementation of the I-Messages (2.b.1) activity, and only the main characteristics of I-Messages were explained. The session concluded with a summary of the key takeaways, emphasizing the importance of active listening and assertive communication in interactions between parents and children.

The feedback was collected by pen-and-paper survey administered at the end of the session. Parents' responses indicate that they particularly appreciated the practical and interactive nature of the

session. They highlighted the usefulness of concrete examples, communication exercises, and real-life demonstrations provided by the facilitators. Participants valued the open discussions, exchange of opinions, and the opportunity for personal reflection. Overall, they enjoyed that the session encouraged active participation, honest dialogue, and offered practical tools they could apply in everyday communication. Parents' suggestions for improvement indicate a desire for longer and more in-depth workshops that provide additional practical information and examples. They expressed interest in including both children and parents in future sessions and emphasized the need to teach children assertive communication and strategies for managing problematic behaviour. Additionally, they suggested covering topics related to online safety and incorporating more real-life, concrete examples to enhance the relevance and applicability of the content.

Pilot with teachers

The pilot with teachers was conducted as a 45-minute workshop involving 6 teachers (May 2025). Instead of directly carrying out the learning activities, facilitators briefly presented and explained each one—its purpose, implementation, and key messages—and gathered teachers' feedback on clarity, usefulness, and feasibility. All six learning activities of Onlife learning unit were tested and evaluated.

The feedback was collected verbally throughout the discussion and by pen-and-paper survey administered at the end of the session. Teachers appreciated the relevance and practicality of the Onlife learning unit, noting that it addresses important and current topics for students. They found the activities engaging and appealing, suitable for capturing students' interest, and valued the ready-made workshop materials and tasks, which make implementation in the classroom easier and more effective. The suggestions for improvement include presenting examples of classroom lessons and outcomes from the activities. It was also suggested that tasks be adapted for younger children and that the individual activities be more thoroughly presented to ensure clarity and ease of implementation.

Conclusion

Pilot 2, involving preadolescents, parents, and teachers, successfully tested activities from the Communication and Onlife learning units, with participants appreciating the interactive approach, real-life examples, and practical communication tools. Preadolescents enjoyed the open discussions and group work, though some wished for more time. Parents valued the session's relevance but suggested longer workshops, more in-depth content, and the inclusion of both children and parents together. Teachers found the Onlife activities engaging and practical but recommended more detailed examples and adaptations for younger children. Key takeaways include the need for longer sessions, age-appropriate adaptations, and a stronger focus on assertive communication, online safety, and behaviour management.

5.3. Pilot 3

General introduction to the pilot

Pilot 3 was composed of two sections: section 3A covers the activities delivered by DOBA's representatives and section 3B covers the activities delivered by teachers who were properly trained and educated in advance (ASAP Educators). In pilot 3, selected learning activities related to the learning units Emotions (impact evaluation purpose), Communication and Onlife were implemented

and evaluated. In section 3A, a total of 95 participants were involved: 72 preadolescents, 15 parents and 8 teachers. And in section 3B, a total of 349 participants were involved: 303 preadolescents, 24 parents and 22 teachers. In the following subsections, mainly the results and insights of section 3A will be presented and explained.

Pilot with preadolescent schoolkids

In section 3A, three sessions with preadolescents were implemented targeting in total 72 participants (there were two distinct classes but in one class, two consecutive sessions were implemented to test the impact of the Emotions learning unit). Their age range was 12-13. One session was conducted in January 2025, and two sessions were conducted in May 2025, each lasting 45 minutes. The first session addressed the activity 2.b.1 of the Communication learning unit (I-messages) – no extra modifications were required; the second and third sessions addressed the Bingo, Emoji and Post-it-notes activities from Emotions learning unit (in the same way as in the Pilot 1).

The feedback was collected by pen-and-paper surveys administered at the end of each session. The feedback from the preadolescents about the I-message activity highlights that they appreciated the open discussion and the opportunity to express their own opinions. They valued being heard and given the chance to share how they felt, which made the activity feel more personal and meaningful. The topic itself was well-received, as it allowed them to reflect on their own emotions and communication styles. Some preadolescents found the activity boring and less interesting and would appreciate more fun and engaging content.

To test the impact of the Emotions learning units (two sessions with Bingo, Emoji and Post-it-activities), evaluation data at T0 were collected in the beginning of session 2, while evaluation data at T1 were collected in the end of session 3. Improvements were seen primarily in areas of public internet awareness, online privacy control, and emotional intelligence. These shifts suggest that the intervention may have strengthened participants' understanding of how to navigate the internet responsibly and emotionally. Declines occurred mostly in understanding the consequences of online actions, the ownership of shared content, and the balance between truth and privacy. These negative changes could indicate a more nuanced, perhaps more relaxed view of the internet, suggesting that some participants may not have fully internalized the risks or responsibilities associated with online behaviour. Overall, while there are mixed results, the positive shifts in understanding internet publicness, privacy, and emotional intelligence are key highlights of the intervention's impact. The negative changes could warrant further exploration to see if they reflect deeper insights or potential areas where participants might need further guidance.

In section 3B, additional 16 sessions with preadolescents (targeting 303 preadolescents altogether) were conducted by ASAP Educators, covering selected activities of Onlife learning unit. These sessions were conducted in May and June 2025.

Pilot with parents

In section 3A, one session with parents was conducted in May 2025, targeting 15 parents. The session, lasting approximately 60 minutes, focused on the learning unit Communication and included the implementation and testing of three activities: Active Listening, Different Response Styles (2.a.1), and I-Messages (2.b.1). It was implemented in a similar way than the session with parents in Pilot 2.

The feedback was collected by pen-and-paper or online survey administered at the end of the session. Parents generally appreciated the interactive and practical approach of the workshop. They liked the open communication, active participation, and clear presentation of assertive communication examples. The facilitators' calm and open attitude was also highlighted positively. Few negative comments were given — most participants said “everything was fine” or “nothing to improve”. A few mentioned that the workshop could have had a clearer focus or structure and that it could last longer. Suggestions included organizing more similar workshops, especially for both parents and children in schools.

In section 3B, two additional sessions with parents (targeting 24 parents altogether) were conducted by ASAP Educators, covering selected activities of Onlife learning unit. These sessions were conducted in May 2025.

Pilot with teachers

In section 3A, one pilot with teachers was conducted as a 45-minute workshop involving 8 teachers (May 2025). Instead of directly carrying out the learning activities, facilitators briefly presented and explained each one—its purpose, implementation, and key messages—and gathered teachers' feedback on clarity, usefulness, and feasibility. All six learning activities of Onlife learning unit were tested and evaluated. The session was implemented in a similar way than the session with teachers in Pilot 2.

The feedback was collected verbally throughout the discussion and by pen-and-paper survey administered at the end of the session. Teachers appreciated the workshop's practical orientation and real-life relevance. They valued the focus on raising awareness about digital footprints and potential pitfalls, as well as the opportunity for open expression and being heard. The interactive, reflective atmosphere and the fresh perspective on familiar situations were highlighted as especially engaging and useful.

In section 3B, six additional sessions with teachers (targeting 22 teachers altogether) were conducted by ASAP Educators, covering selected activities of Onlife learning unit. These sessions were conducted in May and June 2025.

Conclusion

Pilot 3 involved two complementary parts: workshops delivered by DOBA representatives (section 3A) and those implemented by trained ASAP Educators (section 3B). Altogether, over 440 participants—including preadolescents, parents, and teachers—took part in activities focused on Emotions, Communication, and Onlife learning units. The sessions with preadolescents showed notable gains in online privacy awareness and emotional understanding, though some uncertainty remained about online responsibility. Parents valued the workshops' interactive and practical nature, open dialogue, and assertive communication exercises, suggesting longer or more frequent sessions. Teachers highlighted the relevance of topics like digital footprints and the benefits of reflective discussion and practical orientation. Overall, Pilot 3 confirmed the educational value and engagement potential of these activities while revealing areas for refinement in clarity, depth, and sustainability.

6. Conclusions

The comparative analysis of the piloting experiences demonstrates a strong overall convergence in the educational impact of the ASAP Programme. Despite differences in organisational structures, target groups and implementation environments, the Learning Units proved to be highly adaptable and consistently effective in promoting metacognitive awareness, emotional literacy, digital citizenship and critical thinking among preadolescents.

Across all piloting contexts, the modular design of the LUs and the experiential approach facilitated flexible implementation both in formal school settings and in non-formal community environments. Educators reported increased confidence in facilitating reflective processes, improved group climate and greater engagement from students, confirming the applicability of the methodology under varying conditions and timeframes.

The contributions collected across all piloting countries consistently confirm the robustness, adaptability and educational relevance of the ASAP Programme, demonstrating its effectiveness in diverse organisational, cultural and territorial contexts. Partners also identified common challenges—such as limited time availability in schools, the difficulty of involving parents, and the need for additional ready-to-use examples—which will inform future refinements of the materials and training components.

Overall, the multi-country piloting phase validates the scalability and transferability of the ASAP Educational Programme and provides a solid evidence base for the finalisation of the ASAP Handbook.

This report is part of the Erasmus+ project ASAP – *A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education*.

It documents the piloting of the ASAP Educational Programme carried out between February 2023 and June 2025 in the five partner countries (Italy, Croatia, Czechia, Portugal and Slovenia). The piloting activities tested the Programme in formal and non-formal educational settings, involving pre-adolescents, teachers and parents across multiple implementation phases. Through progressive testing, feedback collection and validation processes, the pilots assessed the feasibility, clarity, adaptability and educational impact of the Learning Units, contributing to the refinement, consolidation and scalability of the ASAP Educational Programme.

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